

**AN ISSUE OF CO-EXISTENCE BETWEEN GERMANY
AND UKRAINE DURING THE MEDIEVAL
AND EARLY MODERN PERIODS AS IT IS PRESENTED
IN RESEARCH LEGACY OF VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH
AND MYKHAILO HRUSHEVSKYI**

From the 1840s until the end of 1920s Ukrainian historical thought was in many instances dominated by populist trend. In their works academic representatives of this trend concentrated on the analysis of events related to the lives of people, predominantly the peasants; with special interest and sympathy they depicted popular riots, revolts, and revolutions¹. Professor of Kharkiv and Kyiv universities Mykola Kostomarov (1817–1885) has traditionally been considered the founder of populist movement in Ukrainian historical thought. However, it cannot go unnoticed that populist ideology was more clearly defined and elaborated by famous Ukrainian historians, Professor of Kyiv University (1878–1908) Volodymyr Antonovych (1834–1908) and Professor, Chair of Ukrainian history at Lviv University (1894–1914) Mykhaylo Hrushevskyi (1866–1934). They compared Ukrainian people with ‘Samson who breaks the chains of slavery’ and unified all the Ukrainians in their own populist-socialist manner denying the right of the elite, especially the nobility, to be called Ukrainians.

¹ Starting from 1840 a new populist concept in Ukrainian historical thought became an alternative to the older one, namely Little Russian concept, that emerged as a reaction to incorporating The Hetmanate by Catherine II in 1783. Populists consciously opposed people and elite as they were convinced that everything that rose above people was parasitic, morally fallen and not Ukrainian. Moreover, they ignored the problem of elite way in nation-building in Ukraine. (See: VOLODYMYR POTUL'NYC'KYI, ‘Das ukrainische historische Denken im 19. und 20. Jahrhundert: Konzeptionen und Periodisierung’, *Jahrbücher für Geschichte Osteuropas*, 45, 1 (1997): 13–30).

In his writings Volodymyr Antonovych mentions the historical ties that had been established between the Ukrainians and the Germans since the Middle Ages. He notes that Grand Princess of Kyiv Olha (Olena in baptism) sent diplomatic embassy to the German Emperor Otto I². In this context the scholar refers to the sixteenth century German travellers who visited Kyiv and reported on it at that point in time. In particular, he specifies that “German travellers (Herberstein, Heidenstein et al.) described the ruins that encumbered the highland part of Kyiv and regretted the decline of splendour of this once famous and well-known city”³, “of which only traces of churches, abandoned monasteries and buildings remained”⁴.

Antonovych highlights a reasonably positive impact of the spread of German culture across the Ukrainian lands on Ukrainians in the late Middle Ages. The formation of the Ukrainian townsmen and their worldview as the residents of regimental and centesimal towns is linked to the development of towns which had a privilege of self-government by Magdeburg Law. Notably, the granting of Magdeburg Law, as emphasized by Antonovych, was initiated with the intention to inhibit the decay and decline of towns. ‘The time when Magdeburg rights were granted was the time of decline in communal system in each area. Thus, granting of the above-mentioned privilege to towns (obtained by ten Ukrainian towns – *V. P.*) was intended to prevent the final suppression of town law by martial law and to keep the first one from being destructed and enslaved due to the pressure of senior officials (starostas) as representatives

² VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, ‘Kyiv v dokhrystyyanskyi chas [Kyiv in Pre-Christian Time]’, [in:] VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, *Moya spovid. Vybrani istorychni ta publitsystychni pratsi [My Confession. Selected Historical and Journalistic Works]*, Kyiv, 1995, p. 587.

³ VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, ‘Kyiv, yoho dolya i znachennya z XIV po XVI stolittya (1362–1569) [Kyiv, its fate and importance from the fourteenth to the sixteenth century]’, [in:] VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, *Moya spovid.*, p. 535.

⁴ VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, ‘Kyiv, yoho dolya i znachennya’ (as in footnote 3), p. 571.

of the second one⁵. As the author underlines, Magdeburg rights restored the largely lost rights and privileges of the townsmen⁶, as the period of its introduction coincides with the period of decline in the communal system of life in every sphere⁷. Positively assessing the idea of Magdeburg Law, Antonovych also mentions a very democratic, in his opinion, rule in the Ukrainian lands by Saxon Elector Augustus II (1697–1706; 1710–1733), who was distinguished by his ‘religious tolerance and respect for freedom of conscience of his subjects’⁸. Furthermore, the scholar enunciates the civilizational mission of Ivan Mazepa, who attended to the next generation of Ukrainian nobility, for the Ukrainian lands. In an attempt to undertake this mission under hetman’s influence, officers sent their sons to foreign, primarily German, universities; for the same purpose Mazepa called foreign nobility up for service⁹.

Antonovych argues that statelessness is naturally inherent in the Ukrainian people. The author notes that it is not infrequent that state borders do not coincide with national boundaries and divides the then existing states into three main types: a) several countries emerged on the territory of one nationality (e. g. Prussia, Bavaria, Saxony, Württemberg and other small German states, England, the USA, Serbia, and Montenegro); b) within the state there is no separate nationality with corresponding name, but rather a group of different nationalities united by common public authority (Austria, Switzerland); c) there are nationalities that do not form an individual state, but become parts of one or more states established by other national-

⁵ VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, ‘Issledovaniye o gorodakh Yugo-Zapadnogo kraia [Research on the towns of South and Western Region]’, [in:] *Monografii po istorii Zapadnoy i Yugo-Zapadnoy Rossii [Monographs on the history of South and Western Russia]*, Kyiv, 1885, p. 165.

⁶ VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, *Issledovaniye o gorodakh v Yugo-Zapadnoy Rossii (po aktam 1432–1789 g.) [Research on the towns of South and Western Russian (based on the acts of 1432–1789)]*, Kyiv, 1870, p. 26.

⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 49.

⁸ VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, *Moya spovid. Vybrani istorychni ta publitsystychni pratsi. [My Confession. Selected Historical and Journalistic Works]*, Kyiv, 1995, p. 478.

⁹ VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, *Pro kozatski chasy na Ukrayini [On Cossack times in Ukraine]*, Kyiv, 1991, p. 157.

ities: these are stateless nationalities¹⁰. That is the reason why Ukraine, as a stateless nationality, could not potentially follow German state formation example, as ‘the German people once disintegrated into 38, now two (states – *V. P.*), and yet they have not lost their national unity’¹¹. Additionally, Ukraine might only be regarded as an ethnographic nationality; the point at issue is not about the revival of state-forming nation, but the revival of ethnographic nation. The revival, according to Antonovych, consists in the fact that ‘every ethnographic unit requires to be granted the right for having its own culture; thus, national legislation should secure all the rights and needs’¹².

By giving his own definitions to the terms ‘nationality’, ‘nation’ and ‘state’ Antonovych suggests the following: ‘there are diametrically opposed theories on how to define the word nationality. The first theory, conventionally known as French-Russian theory, is most commonly followed by people who live in centralized states; according to it, nation is what makes the state. It is a state-national theory. The second theory, to which predominantly German, British, and Italian scholars adhere, is so-called ethnographic theory. It advocates for the fact that any group of people, which makes one type, forms a nation. Hence, in compliance with this theory nationality is brought into existence by nature, not by state’¹³. Accordingly, the definition of state is given in a similar manner¹⁴.

¹⁰ The third type, according to Antonovych, includes Little Russian (Ukrainian – *V. P.*) ethnic group, which in the middle of the seventeenth century, being deprived of state-formation instinct, voluntarily declined the formation of its own state and acceded to the Russian Empire without conquest or fight. See: VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, *Moya spovid...*, p. 157–158.

¹¹ VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, *Pro kozatski chasy*, p. 209.

¹² *Ibid.*, p. 209.

¹³ *Ibid.*, p. 208. Antonovych’s ideas resonate with the ideas of the French Encyclopedia contributor Marie Jean Condorcet (1743–1794), as well as romanticist Augustin Thierry (1795–1856). The latter wrote back in 1820 that ‘the real story is not the history of the state, but of the nation’, and defined the French nation as the outcome of ‘the struggle between the various national tribes (‘races’) and the classes they formed’. See: RÜDIGER VON BRUCH, RAINER A. MÜLLER, *Historiker Lexikon. Von der Antike bis zum 20. Jahrhundert*, München, 1991, S. 314.

¹⁴ ‘The state, – he wrote, – is not a consequence of natural phenomena: it is the product of human mind, formed according to the requirements of historical life; this is an alliance, to which people of one or many nationalities entered with the aim

Being a positivist and evolutionist, Antonovych believed in the progress of the Western European type based on secular education and civilization. Thereby, he clearly illustrates the importance of this issue with the example of the brightest moment in the history of Ukrainian Cossacks (Khmelnyskyi Uprising), when ‘the historical circumstances favoured (Ukraine – *V. P.*) in the best possible way; however, the fundamental idea of the Ukrainian people has never been brought to life due to the apparent deficiency of cultural development, convictions and endurance. The lack of civilization is defined in two ways: in the first one it is noticed that personal selfishness prevails over public affairs; the selfishness manifested itself in the desire of senior officers to mature to nobility, in the attempts of government officials to seize someone else’s lands, to turn Cossacks into the Commonwealth subjects and to make them serfs. ... On the other hand, the lack of civilization impeded the expression of people’s desires in well-defined terms. One might observe that the then community was not capable of codifying its own customary law, which could have been applied by Cossacks if needed; therefore, the society had to repeatedly refer to the alien and hostile Code, more specifically to the Statute of Lithuania, that authorized a class and gentry system, which, in fact, triggered the struggle (with Poland – *V. P.*). Therefore, it is seen that a significant internal discipline is demanded in order to put democratic principles into effect. The tragic denouement of Ukrainian history is the consequence of people’s inability to develop their thorough civilization or their own sound discipline, as those who were in charge and assumed responsibility for people’s fate had a rather insufficient reserve of culture’¹⁵. Arguing that each nation produces its fundamental idea, Antonovych considers the principle of wide democracy to be the one for Ukrainians. Nonetheless, it failed to lead to the formation of independent state over the periods of Zaporozhian Sich or Khmelnyskyi Uprising¹⁶.

to provide external security and internal prosperity’. VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, *Tvory [Works]*, vol. 1, Kyiv, 1932, p. 282.

¹⁵ VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, *Pro kozatski chasy*, p. 20–21.

¹⁶ VOLODYMYR ANTONOVYCH, *Tvory*, p. 283.

Exploring the relationship of Ukrainians with neighbouring nations, another prominent representative of populism trend in Ukrainian historical thought, namely Mykhailo Hrushevskiy, proves the existence of a certain spiritual unity that had always, in his opinion existed between the Ukrainian ethnic element and Western European life. He believes that in accordance with temperament and historical ties Ukrainian people belonged to Western European or simply European circle; although, he does acknowledge that substantial impact on the history and culture of the Ukrainian people was made by those people who lived east of Ukraine, including Russians. Simultaneously, Hrushevskiy views Ukrainian nation as a community primarily in historical and political terms, paying far less attention to ethnological and national-psychological issues¹⁷. It is nationality, in Hrushevskiy's opinion, that should be the basis and ground for political, economic and cultural development.

Another aspect is that Hrushevskiy directly relates the notion of 'people' to the concept of 'state'. Being a populist and socialist, Hrushevskiy believes that the political state power is an ultimate evil in itself rather than a positive factor for the formation of social and public life, where the focus should be on the rights of a single unit as a constituent of masses. Advocating autonomy based on ethnic principle, as the Ukrainian people, according to the historian, is a separate ethno-cultural unit, Hrushevskiy believes that political institutions should rely upon the principles of autonomy and federalism.

In diachronic terms, while defining the stages of Ukrainian statehood that took place throughout history (Kyivan Rus' with the continuation in Galicia in the twelfth-fourteenth centuries, state of Bohdan Khmelnytskyi in the seventeenth century, and Central Rada of Ukraine in 1917) Hrushevskiy acknowledges the significance of

¹⁷ The notion of 'the people' (narodnist' – strongly identified with the peasantry – *V. P.*) is of interest to Hrushevskiy as a certain national form; therefore, for him the Ukrainian people are often associated with the notion of nationality. 'I just want to remind, – Hrushevskiy writes, – that even if one considers nationality to be a lower form, it is vital to provide the freedom of national self-identification to all nationalities which constitute the state'. See: MYKHAILO HRUSHEVSKYI, *Osvobozhdenie Rossii i ukrainskiy vopros: statyi i zametki [Liberation of Russian and the Ukrainian question: articles and notes]*, St Petersburg, 1907, p. 71, 72.

state in shaping otherwise passive masses. In particular, the state imposed political, state, cultural, economic and legal system upon its people¹⁸.

Afterwards, the scholar evaluates the psychological properties of Ukrainian people. He identifies the inherent features of dignity and respect for the dignity of others, and love for certain traditionally established external forms, the so-called 'legal things' (etiquette, good manners, love of cleanliness, order, beauty of life, etc.)¹⁹. These features, according to Hrushevskiyi, bring Ukrainians nearer to Western culture – to some extent to the Germans, known for their solidity, efficiency, love of comfort, order, cleanliness; to some degree to the Roman culture – craving for form, elegance, desire to bring beauty into everything in order to highlight every sphere of life, as well as bright, clear and joyful outlook²⁰.

Moreover, to avoid making these statements look simple far-fetched assumptions, the scholar, as always, supports his findings with rather significant empirical material, and concrete facts from the history of Ukrainian people and their culture. He mentions, first of all, the traditional relations of Ukraine with the German and Celtic cultures of Danube Region in prehistoric times, the massive influx of Scandinavian element during the formation of the Kyivan State and at the time of its heyday – the era of Yaroslav the Wise, extremely wide dynastic relationships with the German principalities and other principalities and states that were influenced by German culture. Additionally, the author claims that in the twelfth-thirteenth centuries 'relations with the German lands became even more important'²¹.

¹⁸ If, according to Hrushevskiyi, these rules grew up 'on the national grounds' and 'met the needs of people', they were perceived as one's own; if not, then the masses rose up against such rules. See: MYKHAILO HRUSHEVSKYI, 'Vstupnyi vyklad z davnyoyi istoriyi Rusy [Introductory notes to the ancient history of Rus]', *Zapysky Naukovoho Tovarystva im. Shevchenka [Notes of Shevchenko Academic Society]*, vol. 4 (Lviv, 1894): 149.

¹⁹ MYKHAILO HRUSHEVSKYI, *Na porozhi novoyi Ukrainy. Hadky i mriyi [On the threshold of new Ukraine. Musings and dreams]*, Kyiv, 1918, p. 20.

²⁰ *Ibid.*

²¹ *Ibid.*, p. 13.

Most notably, as reported by Hrushevskiyi, German influences were observed in the Galician – Volhynian Kingdom (in another sources – Principality – *V. P.*) that, in contrast to Dnieper Ukraine had fully entered the sphere of western European life. Regarding large Western European, in particular German, colonies in Western Ukraine, Hrushevskiyi notes that at the end of the fourteenth century the centre of Galicia, Lviv, became a typical German city and remained such during the fifteenth and partially the sixteenth century, simultaneously being a cultural centre of Ukraine²². Analyzing further cultural relations of Ukraine with the West, the scholar concludes that it supported direct relations with Western Europe, primarily with Germany, as well as Italy, experienced Italian and German Renaissance, German Reformation, shared the life of the West, and borrowed their samples for its culture. Thus, these links found expression in architecture, art, and culture of Galicia. In particular, he notes that one of the greatest Ukrainian poets Ivan Franko (1856–1916) ‘was a disciple of Western European, primarily German, culture; he had a native speaker level in German; he was at home in the German literature’²³. However, Hrushevskiyi is fair in claiming that German influences in Ukraine ‘were not borrowed in a slavish way’; they were rather creatively modified by the peculiarities of Ukrainian national spirit²⁴.

It could not go unnoticed that, in scholar’s vision, in exerting the influence on Ukrainian spiritual life the highest value is placed on German science. In particular, he notes that due to the influences of the University of Königsberg (Albertina), founded in the middle of the sixteenth century with the aim of spreading Protestant ideas in the lands of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania, a number of prominent Protestant scientists arrived to Eastern Ukraine to establish themselves as authoritative figures in cultural and church life

²² МΥΚΗΑΙΛΟ ΗΡΥΣΗΒΣΚΥΙ, *Na porozi*, p. 14.

²³ МΥΚΗΑΙΛΟ ΗΡΥΣΗΒΣΚΥΙ, ‘Apostolovi pratsi [To the apostle of labour]’, [in:] ΜΥΚΗΑΙΛΟ ΗΡΥΣΗΒΣΚΥΙ, *Trovy u 50 tomakh. Seriya istorychni studiyi ta rozvidky (1924–1930) [Works in 50 volumes. Series of historical studies and research]*, Lviv, 2015, vol. 10, b. 1, p. 132. First published in: *Ukrayina*, b. 6 (1926): 3–20.

²⁴ ΜΥΚΗΑΙΛΟ ΗΡΥΣΗΒΣΚΥΙ, *Na porozi*, p. 14.

of Ukraine²⁵. This university, which enrolled 250 Ukrainian students over the period of late sixteenth to late eighteenth century, Hrushevskyi maintains, was extensively focused on disseminating German Protestantism to the east and networking with the so-called ‘Greeks’²⁶ (Eastern Orthodox Church).

Spiritual and scientific relations between Königsberg (East Prussia in general) and Ukraine, the scholar remarks, intensified considerably in the second half of the seventeenth century. At that point in time educated immigrants from Prussia, impelled by scientific and religious interests, not merely moved to Ukraine and joined the ranks of Ukrainian cultural figures, but also became an integral part of Ukrainian cultural and national movement. Thereby, Hrushevskyi calls particular attention to two Prussian immigrants who ‘won lasting memories’: Innokentiy Gisel, a long-time abbot of the Kyiv Pechersk Lavra (Cave Monastery), and Adam Zernikaw (1652–1691), a distinguished theologian of the second half of the seventeenth century²⁷.

Therewith, Hrushevskyi attaches particular importance to the influence of German science and culture on one of the most prominent Ukrainian philosophers of the eighteenth century, namely Hryhoriy Skovoroda (1722–1794). Skovoroda, as Hrushevskyi claims, developed the ideas of German philosophers and mystics Weigel, Böhme and Silesius on the struggle of matter and spirit in a human being, on human duty to fight against materialistic desires and to elevate to spiritual world through self-discovery and inner renewal that should replace futile school science²⁸.

Broadly speaking, the author believes that Ukrainian culture across seventeenth-eighteenth centuries by the end of Hetman pe-

²⁵ MYKHAILO HRUSHEVSKYI, *Istoriya ukrayinskoyi literatury*, tom 6 [*History of the Ukrainian Literature*, vol. 6], [in:] *Kyivska biblioteka davnyoho ukrayinskoho pysmenstva. Studiyi* [*Kyiv library of ancient Ukrainian literature. Papers*], Kyiv, 1995, vol. 1, p. 37.

²⁶ MYKHAILO HRUSHEVSKYI, *Z istoriyi relihiynoyi dumky na Ukrayini* [*From the history of religious thought in Ukraine*], Kyiv, 1992, p. 105.

²⁷ MYKHAILO HRUSHEVSKYI, *Istoriya ukrayinskoyi literatury*, p. 37–38.

²⁸ MYKHAILO HRUSHEVSKYI, *Z istoriyi relihiynoyi dumky*, p. 130.

riod should be related to Western influence, primarily to German and to some extent Italian and French, exerted directly and through Poland. This process was extensively promoted due to economic ties (brisk trade of Ukraine with large German cities of Breslau and Danzig, as well as fairs, where German and Ukrainian merchants had a chance to meet) and cross-cultural links (German universities played a significant role in forming Ukrainian intelligentsia). ‘Only at the end of the eighteenth century, – the author notes – these ties weakened and started declining under the pressure of forced Russification of Ukrainian life; Ukrainian life and culture entered the Great Russian period’²⁹. In 1918 Hrushevskiy (at that time head of The Central Council) asserts that Ukraine could renew its ties with the Western world with revived vigour and energy, as well as apply its reserves of knowledge, culture, social instinct, and discipline. However, he warns that ‘we do not need to adjust our lives to some Western European pattern, not even the German one’³⁰ because he believes that release from the forced Russian subjugation should not be replaced by another dependence, even if it is voluntary. Therefore, Hrushevskiy recommends to Ukrainians to pattern themselves on the USA in addition to Germany. These two countries, in his opinion, might be two good schools for Ukrainian people: the first one being more theoretical, the second – more practical³¹.

In the context of determining the international vector for Ukraine, scholar’s dominant idea was the commitment to Black Sea-Baltic Federation, including Ukraine, Belarus and Lithuania, located geographically between Europe and Russia. Noting that these countries were Ukraine’s allies at the beginning of their historical life and ‘old friends in the Polish Union’³², he draws attention to the similarities of historical fate of these three nations and noted that they are ‘adopted children of historical Poland’³³. Ukraine’s takeover of

²⁹ МΥΚΗΑΙΛΟ ΗΡΥΣΗΕΥΣΚΥΙ, *Na porozi novoyi Ukrayiny*, p. 15.

³⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 22.

³¹ *Ibid.*, p. 23.

³² ΜΥΚΗΑΙΛΟ ΗΡΥΣΗΕΥΣΚΥΙ, ‘Ukraine, Weissrussland, Litanen’, *Ukrainische Rundschau*, B. 2 (1909): 51.

³³ *Ibid.*

Germany's theoretical experience and US practical experience combined with the prospect of future federal state union of three nations in Black Sea-Baltic Region, where the dominant role was assigned to Ukrainian nation as being more numerous and richer in economic resources, was one of scholar's most cherished dreams.

Conclusions

1. The historians of populist trend, being proponents of social approach and discussing historical ties that had developed between the Ukrainians and the Germans throughout history, emphasized highly positive impacts of German culture on Ukrainian people in the Middle Ages. It includes the vast dynastic ties with German principalities, the influence of Magdeburg Law on the formation of Ukrainian townsmen outlook, and raising a new generation of Ukrainian nobility by Ukrainian hetmans under the influence of German science and culture.

2. Both populists attributed the origins of the Ukrainian nation as a distinct ethnographic and cultural unit to maintaining direct relations between Ukraine and Western Europe, in particular Germany, with the Ukrainian people borrowing the elements of German culture which were ingeniously transformed to reflect distinct features of Ukrainian spirit. Moreover, they recognized that Ukrainian culture of the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries should be associated with Western influences, primary German ones.

3. Both populists expressed regret about the lack of civilization in the development of the Ukrainian people; though, they stated that for Ukraine the German state formation model, where the national unity was preserved regardless the territorial fragmentation into several states, could not be efficiently working, as in case of Ukraine only the revival of ethnographic, not state, nation could be the point of discussion. However, they put forward the idea of the Black Sea-Baltic Federation consisting of Ukraine, Belarus and Lithuania, which could be situated between Russia and Germany without explicit commitment to one of these great powers.

4. Populists attempted to prove the existence of a spiritual unity that has always, in their opinion, been present between the

Ukrainian ethnic element of cultural and the German cultural and educational life. Ukraine, as regarded by populists, in its aspiration to form a federal state association should simultaneously adopt Germany's theoretical experience (stock of knowledge, culture and discipline).

5. Ukrainian populists did not believe in the ability of the Ukrainians to become a nation without either German or American assistance. They believed that the Ukrainians would be able to be free from forced Russian dependence if they got instructed by the German theoretical school, and the American practical school.

Володимир ПОТУЛЬНИЦЬКИЙ

Проблема українсько-німецького співіснування в середньовіччі і ранньоновочасні часи в дослідницькій спадщині Володимира Антоновича і Михайла Грушевського

У статті відтворюється образ Німеччини, що склався в контексті створення відповідних наративів провідними українськими національними істориками протягом досліджуваного періоду. На основі аналізу низки оригінальних наукових і публіцистичних праць видатних істориків народницького напрямку Володимира Антоновича і Михайла Грушевського, автор відтворює їхнє бачення Німеччини та німецько-українських стосунків.

Автор доходить висновку, що історики народницького напрямку, будучи апологетами соціального підходу та розкриваючи у своїх працях історичні зв'язки, які склалися між українцями і німцями протягом історії, водночас відзначали і вельми позитивні впливи, які мало для українського народу поширення німецької культури на його землі в епоху середньовіччя. Це і широкі династичні зв'язки з німецькими князівствами, і впливи магдебурзького права на формування світогляду українського міщанства, і плекання українськими гетьманами нового покоління українського дворянства під впливом німецької науки і культури.

Витоки формування українського народу як окремої етнографічно-культурної одиниці обидва учених пов'язували з підтриманням безпосередніх стосунків України з Західною Європою, в першу чергу з Німеччиною, з запозиченням українським народом зразків для

своєї культури у німців, які творчо перероблялися відповідно з особливостями українського народного духу. Вони визнавали, що всю українську культуру XVII–XVIII століть слід пов'язати із західними впливами, головним чином німецькими. Дослідники висловлювали жаль про недостачу цивілізації в розвитку українського народу, але водночас стверджували, що для України німецький приклад державотворення, де була збережена національна єдність при територіальній роздробленості на декілька держав не може підходити, оскільки в українському випадку можна говорити лише про відродження не державної нації, а лише етнографічної.

Народники доводили наявність певної духовної єдності, що завжди, на їхню думку, існувала між українським етнічним елементом і німецьким культурно-освітнім життям. Україні, на переконання народників, у стремлінні до федеративного державного об'єднання під своїм проводом трьох народностей (України, Білорусії та Литви) слід одночасно переймати теоретичний досвід (запас знань, культури, дисципліни) Німеччини. Українські народники не вірили у спроможність українців самим стати нацією без сторонньої – німецької та американської допомоги. Вони вважали, що українці зможуть самі стати нацією і звільнитися від примусової російської залежності, якщо будуть вчитися у німців теоретичної школи, а в американців – практичної. В цілому, слідуючи загальному зразкові східноєвропейської історіографії і переймаючи національну парадигму, Антонович і Грушевський вважали, що Німеччина всіяко зацікавлена у відділенні України від Росії.

Ключові слова: українська історична думка, народництво, образ Німеччини, німецький вплив, українсько-німецькі взаємини.

Володимир Потульніцький, доктор історичних наук, професор, провідний науковий співробітник Інституту української археографії та джерелознавства ім. М. С. Грушевського НАН України (м. Київ, Україна),

Volodymyr Potulnytskyi, DS in History, Professor, Leading Research Fellow at the M. S. Hrushevsky Institute of Ukrainian Archaeography and Source Studies of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (Kyiv, Ukraine),